

Dual-mode electrochemical and SERS detection of PFAS using functional porous substrate

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A dual approach for simple, express, and portable detection of PFAS is proposed.
- The approach is based on mutually complementary methods: EIS and SERS.
- The specially designed plasmon- and electrochemically active substrates were used.
- Utilization of EIS allows detection of PFAS up to a concentration of 10^{-10} M.
- Subsequent SERS measurements enhance the detection reliability.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Human activity is the cause of the continuous and gradual grooving of environmental contaminants, where some released toxic and dangerous compounds cannot be degraded under natural conditions, resulting in a serious safety issue. Among them are the widely occurring water-soluble perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), sometimes called “forever chemicals” because of the impossibility of their natural degradation. Hence, a reliable, expressive, and simple method should be developed to monitor and eliminate the risks associated with these compounds. In this study, we propose a simple, express, and portable detection method for water-soluble fluoro-alkyl compounds (PFOA and GenX) using mutually complementary methods: electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS). To implement our method, we developed special substrates based on porous silicon with a top-deposited plasmon-active Au layer by subsequently grafting $-C_6H_4-NH_2$ chemical moieties to provide surface affinity toward negatively charged water-soluble PFAS.

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Subsequent EIS utilization allows us to perform semiquantitative detection of PFOA and GenX up to 10^{-10} M concentration because surface entrapping of PFAS leads to a significant increase in the electrode–electrolyte charge-transfer resistance. However, distinguishing by EIS whether even PFAS were entrapped was impossible, and thus the substrates were subsequently subjected to SERS measurements (allowed by surface plasmon activity due to the presence of a porous Au layer), clearly indicating the appearance of characteristic C–F vibration bands.

1. Introduction

Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a major class of pollutants of increasing global concern because of their extensive use and industrial applications (Chen et al., 2015; Park et al., 2023; Takayose et al., 2012; Yin et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2019). PFAS, sometimes called “forever chemicals,” are highly resistant to degradation and readily bioaccumulate in the environment, where they are gradually consumed, causing health-related risks to humans and animals (Fiedler et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022; Miladinova et al., 2024; Pierozan et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2024). It is almost impossible to manage and control PFAS contamination sources because they are commonly used in most of Teflon-coated products. Therefore, many national regulatory agencies are monitoring the levels of fluoro-alkylated compounds in water and seafood to reduce health risks at least minimally (Bălan et al., 2021; Cordner et al., 2019; Fiedler et al., 2022; Rogers et al., 2021).

Various environmental protection agencies in different states with the most developed healthcare systems have already determined the maximum permissible concentration(s) of PFAS (Bock and Laird, 2022). The maximum permissible standards for PFAS in drinking water are still very different from country to country. For example, in the USA in 2022, the sanitary standards for PFOA were set at 0.004 ng/L, while in the Germany this value is 100 ng/L. Considering the existing limitations and prescriptions, there is a need to develop a reliable, fast, and simple method for monitoring PFAS concentrations in water (Ogunbiyi et al., 2023).

Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry methods are typically used for PFAS detection, which requires the collection of samples for subsequent analysis (Androulakakis et al., 2022; Forster et al., 2024; Jacob et al., 2019). Although these methods achieve excellent sensitivity, they are time-consuming, costly, and require complicated sample preparation in relatively high volumes (Onghena et al., 2012). Thus, great attention has been devoted to developing alternative, express, and simple methods, such as electrochemical, spectroscopic, and colorimetric (Hong et al., 2022; Renganathan et al., 2024; Shanbhag et al., 2022; Takayose et al., 2012; Tian et al., 2024; Wei et al., 2023; Yin et al., 2021). Ideally, the detection method should fulfil the requirements of real-time analysis using portable devices, low detection limits, and overall simplicity (Breshears et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2015; Law et al., 2022; Rex Shanlee et al., 2024; Wei et al., 2023).

As an alternative, different electrochemical methods were employed for PFAS detection to fulfill the aforementioned requirements, including various voltammetry deviations and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis (Clark and Dick, 2020; Fang et al., 2016a; Fanga et al., 2017; Gogoi et al., 2023; Islam and Arrigan, 2022; Kazemi et al., 2020). EIS is commonly employed with utilization of specific anchors or coatings (grafted to working electrode surface), ensuring electrode surface affinity toward PFAS. Although this method often suffers from lower specificity because of the nonspecific sorption of alternative molecules, it has achieved high sensitivity and capability in in-situ analysis (Chandrasekar et al., 2023; Kazemi et al., 2020; Shanbhag et al., 2022; Viada et al., 2020). As an alternative, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) distinguishes the exact molecular structure of surface-entrapped molecules (i.e., fluoro-alkyl substances) (Bhavaya et al., 2023). This method achieved a very low detection limit and, therefore, can be considered an interesting alternative for PFAS detection (Burtsev et al., 2019; Elashnikov et al., 2017; Fang et al.,

2016b; Fang et al., 2017; Feng et al., 2023; Guselnikova et al., 2020; McDonnell et al., 2023).

In this study, we proposed rapid, express, and reliable PFAS detection by combining EIS and SERS. PFAS were entrapped on the surface and immediately revealed by EIS using specifically functionalized conductive and plasmon-active electrodes. In the case of positive detection of PFAS, the pSi/Au–C₆H₄–NH₂ substrates were subjected to SERS, allowing the definitive decision that even PFAS molecules were entrapped on the sensor surface.

2. Experimental

Supplementary information (SI) provides a detailed description of the preparation and characterization of substrates. Briefly, we subjected the Si wafers (p-type, boron-doped, (100) crystallographic orientation, resistivity 0.05–1 $\Omega \times \text{cm}$, Siegert wafer) for electrochemical etching in HF solution (volume ratio: 1 H F:20 DMF) under the following conditions: 2 mA, 15 min. Photos of the experimental setup are given in Fig. S1. Subsequently, we deposited thin Au films on porous electrode surfaces using magnetron sputtering. The deposition conditions were optimized for more efficient surface plasmon excitation (see SI). In the final step of porous Si wafer preparation, we grafted –C₆H₄–NH₂ chemical moieties using the diazonium chemistry approach.

We used perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and ammonium salt of hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid (GenX) as model compounds. Both analytes were dissolved in water at different concentrations (10^{-6} – 10^{-10} M/L). The concentration range was set to the available limits of analytes in drinking water worldwide (Cordner et al., 2019; World Health Organization, 2020). Substrates were immersed in the H₂SO₄ solution, adjusted to pH = 4 to protonate the grafted amino group, and to the PFOA or GenX solution and then immediately subjected to EIS measurements at $E_{\text{dc}} = -0.3$ V; $E_{\text{ac}} = 0.02$ V; 1 MHz–0.001 Hz. Subsequently, substrates were removed from the solution, slightly washed with deionized water, dried under ambient conditions, and subjected to SERS measurements (wavelength: 785 nm; power: 2 mW; scan rate: 7s; 10 \times average).

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 presents the schematic of the proposed experimental concept. First, a porous Si (pSi) surface was created using electrochemical etching to increase the surface–electrolyte contact area and provide roughed surface morphology (one of the conditions of surface plasmon excitation Fig. S2). The conditions of Si etching were optimized to reach highest SERS enhancement (Table S1). Second, the Au layer with optimized thickness (Fig. S3 and Fig. S4) was deposited on the pSi wafer to increase surface conductivity and provide a plasmon absorption band. Third, –C₆H₄–NH₂ chemical moieties were grafted onto the surface using the diazonium chemistry approach, providing surface sorption sites for COO[–]-terminated fluoro-alkyl chains. Diazonium chemistry provides strong covalent bonding of grafted moieties to the surface (unlike the common thiol method, which provides less stable attachment of grafted organic compounds to the surface) (Buravets et al., 2023; Kalachyova et al., 2017; Mesnage et al., 2012). Subsequently, express EIS detection was performed to detect the potential entrapment of water-soluble fluoro-alkyl compounds and followed by SERS measurements to confirm that even PFAS were immobilized on the substrate surface (description of the principles of both, SERS and EIS is given in SI).

The surface morphologies of pSi/Au and pSi are presented in Fig. 2a and Fig. S5. As is evident, the pores became slightly narrower after the Au deposition. The surface of “finally used” pSi/Au is highly porous with the pore size distributed in the 80 ± 30 nm range. Additional electrochemical measurements indicate $\times 2.5$ times higher surface area than flat gold (Table S2 and Fig. S6). The EDX mapping reveals that the surface is homogeneously coated with an Au layer. The UV-vis spectrum, measured in back-reflected light, indicates the presence of a broad absorption band, located at the 490–650 nm wavelength range (Fig. 2b). The appearance of this band after Au deposition confirms its plasmon-related nature. Finally, $-C_6H_4-NH_2$ anchor grafting was confirmed by SERS and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements (Fig. 2c and d), indicating the successful immobilization of these chemical moieties. In particular, after surface grafting, the appearance of characteristic vibration bands of the Au–C band stretch ($404-410$ cm^{-1}), $-NH_2$ stretch ($1240-1360$ cm^{-1}), and Ar ring stretch ($1100-1330$ cm^{-1} and $1517-1620$ cm^{-1}) are clearly visible. In addition, C–N stretching vibrations manifest themselves as medium peaks at 1170 cm^{-1} , whereas those at 477 cm^{-1} and 413 cm^{-1} are related to out-of-plane deformation vibrations of the aromatic ring. Additionally, the XPS survey spectra revealed an apparent increase in the surface carbon concentration and the appearance of a characteristic nitrogen signal after organic moieties grafting, confirming the attachment of organic moieties.

Next, we verified the functionality of the created surface for dual-mode PFAS detection. In our detection approach, grafted $-NH_2$ will ensure positive surface charging (after preliminary protonation, confirmed by SERS measurements, Fig. S7) and entrapment of PFOA and GenX molecules by interacting with the negatively charged $-COO^-$ chemical moieties in their structure. The created substrates were immersed in the corresponding solutions of PFOA and GenX with different concentrations and analytes entrapment was confirmed as an apparent shift of plasmon absorption bands, due to the changes in the local environment of the plasmon active Au layer (Fig. S8). This shift should be attributed to analytes entrapments, since in the case of the $-NH_2$ protonation the position of the plasmon absorption band remains almost unchanged (Fig. S9). Surface entrapment of PFAS was additionally confirmed by XPS measurements (Table S3). In the next step, the EIS spectra were measured with or without the addition of different concentrations of PFOA and GenX. The results obtained are presented in

Fig. 3a and b and indicate the apparent increase in charge-transfer resistance between the electrode and electrolyte surface (evident as an increase in the corresponding semicircle radii). We observed an increased charge-transfer resistance for both compounds, which should be attributed to the surface sorption/immobilization of both analytes, with the related appearance of an additional dielectric layer between the electrolyte and the electrode surface (with a highly hydrophobic fluoro-alkyl chain), which blocks the charge transfer. As is also evident, surface blocking was observed even for 10^{-10} M concentration (corresponding to 41.4 ng/L) concentrations which should be monitored according to the most protection agencies. Published detection limits are compared in Table S4.

Calibration curves, plotted as a dependence of characteristic semicircles radii on PFOA and GenX concentrations, are presented in Fig. 3c and d. We observed closed-to-linear dependencies in both cases, indicating semiquantitative detection ability in the 10^{-6} – 10^{-10} M concentration range. Moreover, we performed all measurements with a small, portable potentiostat (size: $16 \times 9.5 \times 4$ cm^3 ; weight: 0.5 kg), allowing potential out-of-door express detection. We also evaluated the importance of surface functionalization with amino groups. The control measurement performed on pSi/Au (without substrate grafting) indicates slight changes in the EIS curves after analyte exposure (Supplementary Fig. S10). Therefore, without preliminary surface grafting, the surface entrapment of PFAS also proceeds, but with significantly lower efficiency, highlighting the importance of surface modification for PFOA and GenX detection.

The previously described EIS results demonstrate the detection capability of PFOA and GenX, i.e., PFAS containing water-soluble $-COOH$ chemical groups. The proposed method is simple, expressive, and portable, ensuring a safety-appropriate detection limit. On the other hand, considering the potential real situation, the applicability of the electrochemical-based method can provoke a range of questions. In real conditions and real samples, many molecules with various charges can exist (for example - fatty acids). These molecules can also be trapped by grafted $-NH_2$ groups, significantly increasing charge-transfer resistance. This means that simple EIS can indicate the potential PFOA or GenX presence (as well as a range of other water-soluble PFAS), but using this method is insufficient to assert that even these particular compounds are present. Thus, EIS detection results should be subsequently confirmed/verified by an alternative, ideally another simple and express detection

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the proposed approach for express and reliable PFOA and GenX detection: etching silicon substrate, followed by the depositing and grafting amino groups. The created substrates can entrap PFOA and GenX molecules, subsequently detected by EIS and SERS methods. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Characterization of the created pSi/Au-NH₂ substrate surfaces: (a) SEM measured surface morphology and EDX maps of Au and Si distribution; (b) UV-vis spectra of the initial Si surface and porous Si surface before and after adding and grafting of plasmon-active Au layer; (c) Raman spectra, measured on pSi and pSi/Au surface, before and after grafting with -C₆H₄-NH₂ chemical moieties; (d) survey XPS spectra revealing surface composition of pSi/Au and pSi/Au-C₆H₄-NH₂ substrates.

method that can distinguish molecular structure. Considering the plasmon activity of the created substrates, SERS can be considered a solution that satisfies the aforementioned requirements.

SERS based detection of PFAS is presented in Fig. 4a and d (full spectra and characteristic PFOA and GenX SERS peaks are presented in Fig. S11 and Fig. S12) with a particular attention on the characteristic spectral region, where the appearance of C-F vibration bands can be expected. More informative SERS peaks are located at the 720 and 1100 cm⁻¹ spectral regions (particularly, characteristic peaks at 718 and 1001 cm⁻¹ for PFOA and GenX, respectively), revealing the presence of entrapped PFAS. Both peaks are related to C-F vibration, indicating the entrapment of fluoro-alkyl compounds. The intensity of the characteristic peaks also allowed determination of the initial PFOA and GenX concentrations. Calibration curves are presented in Fig. 4b and e. In both cases, we observed a closed-to-linear response in the 10⁻⁶-10⁻¹⁰ M concentration range, allowing for additional semiquantitative detection. Finally, Fig. 4c and f shows SERS maps measured across a 1 × 1 mm² surface area. A low deviation in the SERS peak intensities across the substrate surface indicated that the pSi/Au-NH₂ surface homogeneously entrapped both PFOA and GenX. Thus, SERS spectra can be collected from three to five randomly selected points, thereby simplifying the detection procedure. Considering the EIS and SERS results obtained using the prepared functional substrate, we can suppose that PFOA and GenX detection (as well as other PFAS) can be performed using express, simple, and sensitive EIS measurements. For the final confirmation that even these compounds caused the changes in the EIS signal, the simple, sensitive, and reliable SERS measurements should be employed. It should also be noted that we used a 785 nm SERS excitation wavelength,

to take into account the potential utilization of the portable Raman spectrometer and avoid degradation of organic molecules. However, similar results of both PFOA and GenX detection can be reached with the utilization of 633 nm excitation wavelength too (Figs. S13 and S14).

We also compared the proposed and commonly-used methods (Table 1). Most reported detection methods suffer from long analysis time, high costs (chromatographic methods), low specificity, and limited detection cross-sensitivity (more expressed optical or electrochemical methods). The approach proposed here eliminates these drawbacks. It is express and reliable, and allows precise recognition of the molecule entrapped. Tables 2 and 3 present the substrates used for the electrochemical and SERS-based detection of PFAS (Fang et al., 2016b; Feng et al., 2023; Glasscott et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Mashkooor et al., 2023; McDonnell et al., 2023; Park et al., 2023; Shanhag et al., 2024, 2022; Thacharakkal et al., 2024; Tian et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). As is evident, a wide range of materials with high conductivity and/or redox activity are used as an electrode material. However, the electrochemical reaction commonly proceeds on the surface of a bare, non-functionalized surface (except the molecularly imprinted Au surface (Glasscott et al., 2020)), which can decrease the detection reliability (in the case of complex, closed to real samples). The SERS detection has been commonly performed with the utilization of plasmon-active noble metal nanoparticles or surfaces, which is close to our approach. In this case, the non-functionalized surfaces have commonly been used too, which may lead to a similar problem as in the case described above.

Fig. 3. (a, b) EIS spectra measured on the pSi/Au-NH₂ surface with or without the addition of various PFOA and GenX amounts; (c, d) corresponding calibration curves, revealing the changes of electrode-electrolyte charge-transfer resistance (i.e., semicircles radii) as a function of PFOA and GenX concentrations (error bars were calculated based on the standard deviation of three repeated measurements for each concentration).

Fig. 4. (a, d) Raman spectra measured on the pSi/Au-NH₂ surface after entrapment of various PFOA and GenX amounts; (b, e) corresponding calibration curves as a function of PFOA and GenX concentrations; (c, f) Raman maps showing the homogeneous intensity of selected peaks at 718 cm⁻¹ and 1001 cm⁻¹ for PFOA and GenX, respectively.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we propose a dual-mode detection method for water-

soluble PFAS: PFOA and GenX. The porous silicon substrate, covered by a thin Au layer and subsequently grafted with -C₆H₄-NH₂ chemical moieties was produced and utilized for this purpose. The porous

Table 1
Comparison of our results with common detection methods.

Principle	Advantages	Disadvantages	Method	Matrice	Limit of detection	Ref.
Chromatographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > High sensitivity > Low LOD > Excellent reproducibility > Multiplex detection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Long analysis time > High cost > Complicated samples preparation 	UHPLC–MS/MS	Distilled water and river water	0.05 pM PFOA	Onghena et al. (2012)
			CLC–MS		0.14 pM PFOA	
Optical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Simple > Portable > Low cost > Variable > Good sensitivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Low specificity > Limited multiplex detection 	Fluorescence	Real water	0.98 nM PFOA	Yang et al. (2024)
			Colorimetric	Distilled water and wastewater	0.133 μM PFOA	Hou et al. (2024)
Electrochemical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Simple > Portable > Fast > Low cost > High sensitivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Bad cross-sensitivity > Limited multiplex detection 	CV	Distilled water	1.07 nM PFOA	Wang et al. (2023)
			CV	Soil, water, Spoiled vegetables, and spoiled fruit	18.3 nM PFOA	Shanbhag et al. (2022)
			LSV	Distilled water and real water	0.048 nM PFOA	Tian et al. (2024)
			DPV	Surface water	250 fM GenX	Glasscott et al. (2020)
Plasmonics (SERS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Label-free > Express and portability > High sensitivity > Real-time detection 		SPCE	Water (lake, river, tap, drinking, and ocean) and blood plasma	1 μM PFOA	Thacharakkal et al. (2024)
			SERS	Distilled water	1.28 pM PFOA	Park et al. (2023)

Table 2
Comparison of different materials used for PFAS detection methods using electrochemical methods.

Method	Material	Limit of detection (linear range)	Ref.
CV	MIP Co/Fe@CNF	1.07 nM PFOA (1×10^{-8} M to 9×10^{-5} M)	Wang et al. (2023)
CV	Hf-doped WO ₃	18.3 nM PFOA (7.0×10^{-8} M to 3.0×10^{-4} M)	Shanbhag et al. (2022)
LSV	Ce-UiO-66-F	0.048 nM PFOA (0.40–450 nM)	Tian et al. (2024)
DPV	(MIP)-modified Au microelectrode	250 fM GenX (1–5000 pM)	Glasscott et al. (2020)
CV	graphene-based carbon paste electrode	10.4 nM PFOA (0.05–500.0 μM)	Shanbhag et al. (2024)
CV	WS ₂ -MWCNT	2.404 pM PFOA (10–120 pM)	Mashkoor et al. (2023)
EIS, chrono-impedance	MXene-AgNP	33 ppq PFOS (50 ppq to 1.6 ppt) or 0.834 ppt GenX (one conc. of 1 ppt)	Khan et al. (2024)

Table 3
Comparison of different materials used for PFAS detection methods using SERS.

Method	Material	Limit of detection	Ref.
SPCE	Ag-Au-NCF	1 fM PFOA	Thacharakkal et al. (2024)
SERS	Ag nano-grass	1.28 pM PFOA	Park et al. (2023)
SERS	AgNPs/Au@AgNRs sandwich structure	0.1 ppm (242 mM) PFOA	Feng et al. (2023)
SERS	optical fibers coated with AgNPs	40 ng/L (0,1 nM) PFOA	Li et al. (2024)
SERS	Ag NPs + Graphene	0.4 ng/L (1 pM) PFOA (range 10^{-3} – 10^{-12} M)	McDonnell et al. (2023)
SERS	AgNP-GO	120 nM PFOA	Fang et al. (2016b)

structure of silicon ensures a high electrode–electrolyte contact area. The Au layer enhances the surface conductivity and introduces plasmonic properties. In turn, surface functionalization with amino groups introduced surface affinity toward the –COO[–] chemical groups of PFOA and GenX. We performed the detection method using mutually

supportive electrochemical and optical methods: EIS and SERS. In particular, EIS measurements allow semiquantitative detection of PFOA and GenX in a simple, express, and equipment-undemanding manner with up to 10^{-10} M detection limits. In this case, the surface entrapment of both targeted compounds led to a significant increase in electrode–electrolyte charge-transfer resistance. However, the EIS-based method cannot distinguish even if PFAS are entrapped (or other negatively charged molecules). Therefore, we performed SERS measurements to solve this problem. In SERS spectra measured on the same substrate (after EIS analysis), the appearance of C–F characteristic vibration bands was evident, allowing the semiquantitative detection of PFOA and GenX presence. Therefore, using EIS and SERS, based on the proposed functional substrates, allows the express, potentially out-of-door detection of fluoro-alkyl compounds in water in a qualitative and semi-qualitative manner with the limit of detection, satisfying the regulatory agencies' requirement.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Karolina Kukralova: Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elena Miliutina:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Olga Guselnikova:** Validation, Conceptualization. **Vasilii Burtsev:** Investigation, Data curation. **Tomas Hrbek:** Investigation, Data curation. **Vaclav Svorcik:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Oleksiy Lyutakov:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

<https://zenodo.org/records/11387287>

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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